

δ -Open Maps and δ -Closed Maps in Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Soft Topological Spaces

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Abstract. This paper introduces and investigates interval-valued neutrosophic soft δ -open and δ -closed maps within the framework of interval-valued neutrosophic soft topological spaces, offering a robust generalization of classical topological mappings under uncertainty. Furthermore, the concept of interval-valued neutrosophic soft $\delta\beta$ -homeomorphism is formulated to extend the notion of topological equivalence in soft and uncertain environments. Several fundamental properties, structural characterizations, and illustrative examples are established to substantiate the theoretical development and to demonstrate its potential applicability in complex decision-making systems governed by indeterminacy and imprecision.

Keywords: interval - valued neutrosophic soft sets, interval - valued neutrosophic soft topological spaces, interval - valued neutrosophic soft δ -open(δ -closed) Maps, interval - valued neutrosophic soft $\delta\beta$ - homeomorphism

1. Introduction

The seminal contribution of Zadeh [16] in 1965, through the formulation of fuzzy sets, established a robust mathematical foundation for handling imprecision and vagueness inherent in real-world phenomena. Building upon this, Atanassov [4] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy sets in 1986 by incorporating non-membership values, thereby enhancing the expressive capability of fuzzy set theory. In response to the need for modeling indeterminacy and inconsistency, Smarandache [11] developed the theory of neutrosophic sets, which further broadened the scope of uncertainty modeling. Subsequently, Smarandache et al. [12] investigated neutrosophic topological spaces based on these enriched set structures. In a parallel stream, Molodtsov [8] introduced soft set theory as a parameterized approach to managing uncertainties, which was

later expanded by Maji [7] through the formulation of neutrosophic soft sets, combining the strengths of both theories.

To better capture interval-based uncertainty, Wang et al. [15] introduced interval-valued neutrosophic sets, which were extended into the soft set framework by Deli [5]. Mukherjee et al. [3] advanced these notions by establishing their topological foundations. In the context of generalized open sets, Vadivel et al. [13] proposed δ -open sets in neutrosophic topology, while Acikgoz et al. [1] examined their properties within neutrosophic soft topological spaces. More recently, Jayasudha and Raghavi [2] introduced interval-valued neutrosophic hypersoft topological spaces, providing a novel structure for modeling multi-parameter uncertainties. Extending this direction, Saeed et al. [9] investigated interval-valued complex neutrosophic sets and their associated soft topologies.

Motivated by these significant developments, the present study introduces and examines the concepts of interval-valued neutrosophic soft δ -open and δ -closed maps. In addition, we define and analyze interval-valued neutrosophic soft $\delta\beta$ -homeomorphisms and establish several characterizations and illustrative examples. These contributions aim to enrich the theoretical landscape of interval-valued neutrosophic soft topological spaces and provide a foundation for further exploration in uncertain and imprecise environments.

2. Preliminaries

This section offers a summary of essential definitions refers to *neutrosophic soft and interval valued neutrosophic soft sets* to ensure thorough understanding.

Definition 2.1. [6]

Assume that \mathbb{W} is the underlying universe and let ϱ be a set of parameters. The collection of all neutrosophic sets within \mathbb{W} is represented by $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{W})$. A neutrosophic soft set, denoted as (S, ϱ) , over \mathbb{W} (abbreviated as NSS) is defined by

$$(S, \varrho) = \{(\varphi, \langle \varepsilon, \mu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon), \sigma_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon), \nu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon) \rangle) : \varepsilon \in \mathbb{W}, \varphi \in \varrho\},$$

where $\mu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon), \sigma_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon), \nu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon) \in [0, 1]$ are called the degree of membership, degree of indeterminacy, and degree of non-membership functions of $S(\varphi)$, respectively. The maximum value for each of μ, σ , and ν is 1.

The inequality $0 \leq \mu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon) + \sigma_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon) + \nu_{S(\varphi)}(\varepsilon) \leq 3$ naturally holds.

Definition 2.2. [5]

Let \mathbb{W} be a universal set, and ϱ be a collection of parameters. The set of all interval-valued neutrosophic soft sets on \mathbb{W} is denoted by $I_v\text{NSS}(\mathbb{W})$. An interval-valued neutrosophic soft set (abbreviated as $I_v\text{NSS}$) on \mathbb{W} is represented by the pair (A, ϱ) , where A is a mapping defined

as $A : \varrho \rightarrow I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$. The collection of all such interval-valued neutrosophic soft sets on \mathbb{W} is represented as $I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$.

Definition 2.3. [5]

An $I_vNSS (A, \varrho)$ over the universe \mathbb{W} is said to be null I_vNSS with respect to ϱ if $\mu_{D(e_1)}(w) = [0, 0], \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w) = [0, 0], \nu_{D(e_1)}(w) = [1, 1] \forall w \in \mathbb{W}, \forall e \in \varrho$ It is denoted by $0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}$.

Definition 2.4. [5]

An $I_vNSS (A, \varrho)$ over the universe \mathbb{W} is said to be universe I_vNSS with respect to ϱ if $\mu_{D(e_1)}(w) = [1, 1], \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w) = [1, 1], \nu_{D(e_1)}(w) = [0, 0] \forall w \in \mathbb{W}, \forall e \in \varrho$ It is denoted by $1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}$.

Definition 2.5. [5]

Let \mathbb{W} be a universe set and ϱ be a set of parameters. Let $(A, \varrho_1), (D, \varrho_2) \in I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$, where $A : \varrho_1 \rightarrow I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$ is defined by $A(e_1) = \{(w, \mu_{A(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w), \nu_{A(e_1)}(w)) : w \in \mathbb{W}\}$ and $D : \varrho_2 \rightarrow I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$ is defined by $D(e_1) = \{(w, \mu_{D(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w), \nu_{D(e_1)}(w)) : w \in \mathbb{W}\}$ where

$\mu_{A(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w), \nu_{A(e_1)}(w), \mu_{D(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w), \nu_{D(e_1)}(w), \in Int([0, 1])$ for $w \in \mathbb{W}$. Then

(i) (A, ϱ_1) is called I_vNS subset of (D, ϱ_2) (denoted by $(A, \varrho_1) \subseteq (D, \varrho_2)$ if $\varrho_1 \subseteq \varrho_2$ and

$$\mu_{A(e_1)}(w) \leq \mu_{D(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w) \leq \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w), \nu_{A(e_1)}(w) \geq \nu_{D(e_1)}(w) \forall w \in \mathbb{W}.$$

Where $\mu_{A(e_1)}(w) \leq \mu_{D(e_1)}(w)$ iff $\inf \mu_{A(e_1)} \leq \inf \mu_{D(e_1)}$ and $\sup \mu_{A(e_1)} \leq \sup \mu_{D(e_1)}$

$\sigma_{A(e_1)}(w) \leq \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w)$ iff $\inf \sigma_{A(e_1)} \leq \inf \sigma_{D(e_1)}$ and $\sup \sigma_{A(e_1)} \leq \sup \sigma_{D(e_1)}$

$\nu_{A(e_1)}(w) \geq \nu_{D(e_1)}(w)$ iff $\inf \nu_{A(e_1)} \geq \inf \nu_{D(e_1)}$ and $\sup \nu_{A(e_1)} \geq \sup \nu_{D(e_1)}$

(ii) their union, represented by $(A, \varrho_1) \cup (D, \varrho_2) = (S, \varrho_3)$, is an I_vNSS over \mathbb{W} , where $\varrho_3 =$

$\varrho_1 \cup \varrho_2$ and $e \in \varrho_3, S : \varrho_3 \rightarrow I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$, where

$$S(e_1) = \{(w, \mu_{S(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{S(e_1)}(w), \nu_{S(e_1)}(w)) : w \in \mathbb{W}\}, \text{ where for } x \in \mathbb{W}$$

$$\mu_{S(e_1)}(w) = \begin{cases} \mu_{A(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_1 - \varrho_2 \\ \mu_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 - \varrho_1 \\ \mu_{A(e_1)}(w) \cup \mu_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 \cap \varrho_1 \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{S(e_1)}(w) = \begin{cases} \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_1 - \varrho_2 \\ \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 - \varrho_1 \\ \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w) \cup \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 \cap \varrho_1 \end{cases}$$

$$\nu_{S(e_1)}(w) = \begin{cases} \nu_{A(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_1 - \varrho_2 \\ \nu_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 - \varrho_1 \\ \nu_{A(e_1)}(w) \cap \nu_{D(e_1)}(w) & \text{if } e \in \varrho_2 \cap \varrho_1 \end{cases}$$

(iii) Their intersection, denoted by $(A, \varrho_1) \cap (D, \varrho_2) = (S, \varrho_3)$, is an I_vNSS over \mathbb{W} where $\varrho_3 = \varrho_1 \cap \varrho_2$ and for $e \in \varrho_3, S : \varrho_3 \rightarrow IVNS(\mathbb{W})$ is denoted by

$$S(e_1) = \{(w, \mu_{S(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{S(e_1)}(w), \nu_{S(e_1)}(w)) : w \in \mathbb{W}\}, \text{ where for } w \in \mathbb{W} \text{ and } e \in \varrho_3$$

$$\inf \mu_{S(e_1)}(w) = \mu_{A(e_1)}(w) \cap \mu_{D(e_1)}(w), \sigma_{S(e_1)}(w) = \sigma_{A(e_1)}(w) \cap \sigma_{D(e_1)}(w) \text{ and } \nu_{S(e_1)} =$$

$$\nu_{A(e_1)}(w) \cup \nu_{D(e_1)}(w).$$

(iv) The complement of (A, ϱ_1) , denoted by $(A, \varrho_1)^c$ is an I_vNSS over \mathbb{W} and is defined as $(A, \varrho)^c = (A^c, \neg\varrho_1)$, where $A^c : \neg\varrho_1 \rightarrow I_vNSS(\mathbb{W})$ is denoted by

$$A^c(e_1) = (w, \nu_{A(e_1)}(w), [1 - \sup\sigma_{A(e)}(w), 1 - \inf\sigma_{A(e_1)}(w)], \mu_{A(e_1)}(w)) : w \in \mathbb{W} \text{ for } e \in \varrho_1$$

Definition 2.6. [3]

An interval valued neutrosophic soft topology (shortly, I_vNSt) on an underlying universe \mathbb{W} is a collection of τ of I_vNS subsets (S, ϱ) of \mathbb{W} where ϱ be the parameters set, satisfying

- (1) $0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)} \in \tau$.
- (2) $[(S, \varrho) \cap (D, \varrho)] \in \tau$ for any $(S, \varrho), (D, \varrho) \in \tau$.
- (3) $\bigcup_{k \in K} (S, \varrho)_k \in \tau$, for every $(S, \varrho_k) : k \in K \subseteq \tau$.

Then $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is known as *interval valued neutrosophic soft topological space* (shortly, I_vNSts) and the elements of τ are known as *interval valued neutrosophic soft open sets* (shortly, I_vNSOS) in \mathbb{W} . A $I_vNSS (S, \varrho)$ is known as *interval valued neutrosophic soft closed set* (shortly, I_vNSCS) if its complement $(S, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSOS .

Definition 2.7. [3]

Let $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ be a I_vNSts & let (S, ϱ) is a I_vNSS on \mathbb{W} . *The interval valued neutrosophic soft interior* of (S, ϱ) (in brief, $I_vNSint(S, \varrho)$) and *the interval valued neutrosophic soft closure* of (S, ϱ) (in brief, $I_vNScl(S, \varrho)$) are represented as

$$I_vNSint(S, \varrho) = \bigcup \{(D, \varrho) : (D, \varrho) \subseteq (S, \varrho) \text{ and } (D, \varrho) \text{ is a } I_vNSOS \text{ in } \mathbb{W}\}.$$

$$I_vNScl(S, \varrho) = \bigcap \{(D, \varrho) : (D, \varrho) \supseteq (S, \varrho) \text{ and } (D, \varrho) \text{ is a } I_vNSCS \text{ in } \mathbb{W}\}.$$

Definition 2.8. [14]

Let $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ be an I_vNSts on \mathbb{W} and let (A, ϱ) is called the I_vNS

- (i) regular-open set (shortly, I_vNSROS) if $(A, \varrho) = I_vNSint(I_vNScl(A, \varrho))$.
- (ii) pre-open set (shortly, I_vNSPOS) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNSint(I_vNScl(A, \varrho))$.
- (iii) semi-open set (shortly, I_vNSSOS) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(A, \varrho))$.
- (iv) α -open set (shortly, $I_vNS\alpha OS$) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNSint(I_vNScl(I_vNSint(A, \varrho)))$.
- (v) β -open set (shortly, $I_vNS\beta OS$) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(I_vNScl(A, \varrho)))$.

The complement of a I_vNSROS (resp. $I_vNSPOS, I_vNSSOS, I_vNS\alpha OS$ and $I_vNS\beta OS$) is called the interval valued neutrosophic soft regular (resp. pre, semi, α and β) closed set (shortly, I_vNSRCS (resp. $I_vNSPCS, I_vNSSCS, I_vNS\alpha CS$ and $I_vNS\beta CS$)) in \mathbb{W}

The family of all I_vNSROS (resp. I_vNSRCS , I_vNSPOS , I_vNSPCS , I_vNSSOS , I_vNSSCS , $I_vNS\alpha OS$, $I_vNS\alpha CS$, $I_vNS\beta OS$ and $I_vNS\beta CS$) of \mathbb{W} is represented by $I_vNSROS(\mathbb{W})$ (resp. $I_vNSRCS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNSPOS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNSPCS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNSSOS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNSSCS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\alpha OS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\alpha CS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\beta OS(\mathbb{W})$ and $I_vNS\beta CS(\mathbb{W})$).

Definition 2.9. [14]

Let (A, ϱ) be a I_vNSSts . Then

- (i) interval valued neutrosophic soft δ -interior of (A, ϱ) (in short, $I_vNS\delta int(A, \varrho)$) is defined by

$$I_vNS\delta int(A, \varrho) = \bigcup \{(D, \varrho) : (D, \varrho) \subseteq (A, \varrho) \ \& \ (D, \varrho) \text{ is a } I_vNSROS \text{ in } \mathbb{W}\}$$

- (ii) interval valued neutrosophic soft δ -closure of (A, ϱ) (in short, $I_vNS\delta cl(A, \varrho)$) is defined by

$$I_vNS\delta cl(A, \varrho) = \bigcap \{(D, \varrho) : (D, \varrho) \supseteq (A, \varrho) \ \& \ (D, \varrho) \text{ is a } I_vNSRCS \text{ in } \mathbb{W}\}$$

Definition 2.10. [14]

An I_vNSS (A, ϱ) is known as I_vNSS

- (1) δ -open set (shortly, $I_vNS\delta OS$) if $(A, \varrho) = I_vNS\delta int(A, \varrho)$.
- (2) δ -pre open set (in short, $I_vNS\delta POS$) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNSint(I_vNS\delta cl(A, \varrho))$.
- (3) δ -semi open set (in short, $I_vNS\delta SOS$) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNS\delta int(A, \varrho))$.
- (4) $\delta\alpha$ open or α -open set (in short, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$ or $I_vNS\alpha OS$) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNSint(I_vNScl(I_vNS\delta int(A, \varrho)))$.
- (5) $\delta\beta$ open or e^* -open set (in short, $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$ or I_vNSe^*OS) if $(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(I_vNS\delta cl(A, \varrho)))$.

The complement of an $I_vNS\delta OS$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta POS$, $I_vNS\delta SOS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$) is called the interval valued neutrosophic soft δ (resp. δ -pre, δ -semi, δ - α and δ - β) closed set (shortly, $I_vNS\delta CS$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta PCS$, $I_vNS\delta SCS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$)) in \mathbb{W} .

The family of all $I_vNS\delta POS$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta PCS$, $I_vNS\delta SOS$, $I_vNS\delta SCS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS$, $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$) of \mathbb{W} is represented by $I_vNS\delta POS(\mathbb{W})$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta PCS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\delta SOS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\delta SCS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS(\mathbb{W})$, $I_vNS\delta\beta OS(\mathbb{W})$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta CS(\mathbb{W})$).

Definition 2.11. [14]

An I_vNSS (A, ϱ) is known as $I_vNS\delta$ -pre(resp. $I_vNS\delta$ -semi, $I_vNS\delta$ - α and $I_vNS\delta$ - β) interior of (A, ϱ) (shortly, $I_vNS\delta Pint(A, \varrho)$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta Sint(A, \varrho)$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha int(A, \varrho)$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta int(A, \varrho)$)) is the union of all $I_vNS\delta POS$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta SOS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$) contained in (A, ϱ) .

Definition 2.12. [14]

An I_vNSS (A, ϱ) is known as $I_vNS\delta$ -pre(resp. $I_vNS\delta$ -semi, $I_vNS\delta$ - α and $I_vNS\delta$ - β) closure of (A, ϱ) (shortly, $I_vNS\delta Pcl(A, \varrho)$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta Scl(A, \varrho)$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha cl(A, \varrho)$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta cl(A, \varrho)$))

is the intersection of all $I_vNS\delta PCS$ (resp. $I_vNS\delta SCS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$) contained in (A, ϱ) .

3. Interval - valued neutrosophic soft δ - open maps in I_vNS ts

In Sections 3, 4 & 5, let $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ and $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be any two I_vNS ts. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be a function. Let (B, ϱ) and (P, ϱ) be an I_vNS sets in I_vNS ts.

Definition 3.1. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be any function. Then, \mathcal{G} is said to be an interval valued neutrosophic soft (resp. δ , $\delta\alpha$, δS , δP & $\delta\beta$ or e^*) open map (in brief, I_vNSO (resp. $I_vNS\delta O$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha O$, $I_vNS\delta SO$, $I_vNS\delta PO$ & $I_vNS\delta\beta O$ or I_vNSe^*O)) if the image of every I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSOS (resp. $I_vNS\delta OS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$, $I_vNS\delta SOS$, $I_vNS\delta POS$ & $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$ or I_vNSe^*OS) in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.

Theorem 3.1. The statements are hold for I_vNSO Mapping.

- (i) Every $I_vNS\delta O$ map is an I_vNSO map.
- (ii) Every I_vNSO map is an $I_vNS\delta SO$ map.
- (iii) Every I_vNSO map is an $I_vNS\delta PO$ map.
- (iv) Every $I_vNS\delta SO$ map is an I_vNSe^*O map.
- (v) Every $I_vNS\delta PO$ map is an I_vNSe^*O map.
- (vi) Every $I_vNS\delta\alpha O$ map is an $I_vNS\delta SO$ map.
- (vii) Every $I_vNS\delta\alpha O$ map is an $I_vNS\delta PO$ map.

But not conversely.

Proof.

- (i) Let (P, ϱ) be an $I_vNS\delta OS$ in \mathbb{W} . Since \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta O$ map, $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta OS$ in \mathbb{T} . Since every $I_vNS\delta OS$ is an I_vNSOS , $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ is an I_vNSOS in \mathbb{T} . Hence \mathcal{G} is an I_vNSO map.

The proofs of other cases are similar. ■

Example 3.1. Let $\mathbb{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\} = \mathbb{T}$, $\varrho = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $I_vNSS (V_1, \varrho)$ in \mathbb{W} and (S_1, ϱ) , (S_2, ϱ) and (S_3, ϱ) in \mathbb{T} are defined as

$$(V_1, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.2]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(V_1, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.2]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (S_1, e_2) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}) \rangle \rangle \\
 (S_2, e_1) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle \rangle \\
 (S_2, e_2) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle \rangle \\
 (S_3, e_1) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle \\
 (S_3, e_2) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}) \rangle \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have $\tau = \{0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, (V_1, \varrho)\}$ and $\sigma = \{0_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, (S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)\}$. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an identity mapping, then \mathcal{G} is I_vNSO map but not $I_vNS\delta O$ map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_1, \varrho)$ is an I_vNSOS in \mathbb{T} but not $I_vNS\delta OS$ in \mathbb{T} .

The following Figure: 1 illustarte $I_vNS\delta O$ sets in interval valued neutrosophic soft topological space.

FIGURE 1. $I_vNS\delta O$ maps in I_vNS ts.

Example 3.2. Let $\mathbb{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\} = \mathbb{T}, \varrho = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $I_vNSS (V_1, \varrho)$ in \mathbb{W} and $(S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)$ and (S_4, ϱ) in \mathbb{T} are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (V_1, e_1) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.8,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}) \rangle \rangle \\
 (V_1, e_2) &= \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.7,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}) \rangle \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(S_1, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.2]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}) \rangle\rangle$$

Then, we have $\tau = \{0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, (V_1, \varrho)\}$ and $\sigma = \{0_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, (S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)\}$. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an identity mapping, then

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta PO$ map but not I_vNSO map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta POS$ in \mathbb{T} but not I_vNSOS in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta PO$ map but not $I_vNS\delta PO$ map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta POS$ in \mathbb{T} but not $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Example 3.3. Let $\mathbb{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\} = \mathbb{T}, \varrho = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $I_vNSS (V_1, \varrho)$ in \mathbb{W} and $(S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)$ and (S_4, ϱ) in \mathbb{T} are defined as

$$(V_1, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.6]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(V_1, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.2]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_2) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_1) = \langle\langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle\rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.6]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}) \rangle \rangle$$

Then, we have $\tau = \{0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, (V_1, \varrho)\}$ and $\sigma = \{0_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, (S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)\}$.

Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an identity mapping, then

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta\beta O$ map but not $I_vNS\delta SO$ map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$ in \mathbb{T} but not $I_vNS\delta SOS$ in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta\beta O$ map but not $I_vNS\delta PO$ map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta\beta OS$ in \mathbb{T} but not $I_vNS\delta POS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Example 3.4. Let $\mathbb{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\} = \mathbb{T}, \varrho = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $I_vNSS (V_1, \varrho)$ in \mathbb{W} and $(S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)$ and (S_4, ϱ) in \mathbb{T} are defined as

$$(V_1, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(V_1, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.5,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.2]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.7,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.8,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.1]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.8,0.9]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_2, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_3, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.1,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.5]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_4, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.5,0.9]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.6,0.9]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.5,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.7,0.8]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}) \rangle \rangle$$

Then, we have $\tau = \{0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, (V_1, \varrho)\}$ and $\sigma = \{0_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, (S_1, \varrho), (S_2, \varrho), (S_3, \varrho)\}$. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an identity mapping, then

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta SO$ map but not I_vNSO map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta SOS$ in \mathbb{T} but not I_vNSOS in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta SO$ map but not $I_vNS\delta\alpha O$ map because $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho) = (S_4, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNS\delta SOS$ in \mathbb{T} but not $I_vNS\delta\alpha OS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.2. A map $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is an I_vNSe^*O iff for every $I_vNSS (P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho)) \subseteq I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho))$.

Proof. Necessity: Let \mathcal{G} be a I_vNSe^*O map and (P, ϱ) be a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Now, $I_vNSint(P, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$ implies $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$. Since \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*OS map, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSe^*O in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ therefore $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho)) \subseteq I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho))$.

Sufficiency: Assume (P, ϱ) is an I_vNSOS of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho) = \mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(P, \varrho)) \subseteq I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho))$. But $I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$. So $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho) = I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho))$ which implies $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSe^*OS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and hence \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*O . ■

Theorem 3.3. If $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is an I_vNSe^*O map then $I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}^{-1}(I_vNSe^*int(P, \varrho))$ for every $I_vNSS (P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.

Proof. Let (P, ϱ) be a I_vNSS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Then $I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Since \mathcal{G} is I_vNSe^*O , $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)))$ is I_vNSe^*O in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and hence $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))) \subseteq I_vNSe^*int(\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))) \subseteq I_vNSe^*int(P, \varrho)$. Thus $I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}^{-1}(I_vNSe^*int(P, \varrho))$. ■

Theorem 3.4. A map $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*O iff for each $I_vNSS (S, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and for each $I_vNSCS (P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ containing $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho)$ there is an $I_vNSe^*CS (B, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $(S, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume \mathcal{G} be a I_vNSe^*O map. Let (S, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{T}, \tau, \varrho)$ and (P, ϱ) is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$. Then, $(B, \varrho) = \mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSe^*CS of $(\mathbb{T}, \tau, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$.

Sufficiency: Assume (V, ϱ) is a I_vNSOS of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{G}^{-1}((\mathcal{G}(V, \varrho))^c) \subseteq (V, \varrho)^c$ and $(V, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. By hypothesis there is a $I_vNSe^*CS(B, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \tau, \varrho)$ such that $((\mathcal{G}(V, \varrho))^c) \subseteq (B, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (V, \varrho)^c$. Therefore $(V, \varrho) \subseteq (\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho))^c$. Hence

$(B, \varrho)^c \subseteq \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho) \subseteq \mathcal{G}((\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho))^c) \subseteq (B, \varrho)^c$ which implies $\mathcal{G}(V, \varrho) = (B, \varrho)^c$. Since $(B, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSE^*OS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence $\mathcal{G}(V, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and thus \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*O map. ■

Theorem 3.5. A map $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O iff $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(I_vNSE^*cl(P, \varrho)) \subseteq I_vNScl(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))$ for every $I_vNSS (P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*O map. For any $I_vNSS (P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$, $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))$. Therefore by theorem 3.4 there exists a $I_vNSE^*CS (S, \varrho)$ in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $(P, \varrho) \subseteq (S, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))$. Therefore we obtain that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(I_vNSE^*cl(P, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho))$.

Sufficiency: Assume (P, ϱ) is a I_vNSS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and (S, ϱ) is a I_vNSCS of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ containing $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)$. Put $(A, \varrho) = I_vNScl(P, \varrho)$, then $(P, \varrho) \subseteq (A, \varrho)$ and (A, ϱ) is I_vNSE^*CS and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(A, \varrho) \subseteq I_vNScl(\mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)) \subseteq (S, \varrho)$. Then by Theorem 3.4, \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*O map. ■

Theorem 3.6. If $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ are two interval - valued neutrosophic soft maps and $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O . If $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^* -irr then $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O map.

Proof. Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O of $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ because $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSE^*O map. Since \mathcal{H} is I_vNSE^* - irr and $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*OS of $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$, $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)) = \mathcal{G}^{-1}(\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))$ is I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*O map. ■

Theorem 3.7. If $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSO and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O maps then $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*O .

Proof. Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSOS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ because \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSO map. Since \mathcal{H} is I_vNSE^*O , $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)) = \mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*OS of $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$. Hence $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSE^*O map. ■

4. Interval - valued neutrosophic soft δ - closed maps

Definition 4.1. Let $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ and $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be any two $I_vNSTs's$. A map $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is said to be an interval - valued neutrosophic soft (resp. δ , $\delta\alpha$, δS , δP and $\delta\beta$ or e^*) closed map (briefly, I_vNSC (resp. $I_vNS\delta C$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha C$, $I_vNS\delta S C$, $I_vNS\delta P C$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta C$ or I_vNSE^*C)) if the image of every I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSCS (resp. $I_vNS\delta CS$, $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS$, $I_vNS\delta SCS$, $I_vNS\delta PCS$ and $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$ or I_vNSE^*CS) in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.

Theorem 4.1. The following statements are hold:

- (i) Every $I_vNS\delta C$ map is an I_vNSC map.
- (ii) Every I_vNSC map is an $I_vNS\delta S C$ map.

- (iii) Every $I_\nu NSC$ map is an $I_\nu NS\delta PC$ map.
- (iv) Every $I_\nu NS\delta SC$ map is an $I_\nu NSe^*C$ map.
- (v) Every $I_\nu NS\delta PC$ map is an $I_\nu NSe^*C$ map.
- (vi) Every $I_\nu NS\delta\alpha C$ map is an $I_\nu NS\delta SC$ map.
- (vii) Every $I_\nu NS\delta\alpha C$ map is an $I_\nu NS\delta PC$ map.

Proof.

(i) Let (P, ϱ) be an $I_\nu NS\delta CS$ in \mathbb{W} . Since \mathcal{G} is $I_\nu NS\delta C$ map, $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ is an $I_\nu NS\delta CS$ in \mathbb{T} . Since every $I_\nu NS\delta CS$ is an $I_\nu NSCS$, $\mathcal{G}(P, \varrho)$ is an $I_\nu NSCS$ in \mathbb{T} . Hence \mathcal{G} is an $I_\nu NSC$ map.

The other cases are similar. ■

The following Figure: 2 illustarte NSZO sets in neutrosophic soft topological space.

FIGURE 2. $I_\nu NS\delta C$ maps in $I_\nu NS$ Sts.

Example 4.1. In Example 3.1, \mathcal{G} is $I_\nu NSC$ mapping but not $I_\nu NS\delta C$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_\nu NSCS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_1, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_\nu NS\delta CS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Example 4.2. In Example 3.2,

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_\nu NS\delta PC$ mapping but not $I_\nu NSC$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_\nu NS\delta PCS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_\nu NSCS$ in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_\nu NS\delta PC$ mapping but not $I_\nu NS\delta\alpha C$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_\nu NS\delta PCS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_\nu NS\delta\alpha CS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Example 4.3. In Example 3.3,

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta\beta C$ mapping but not $I_vNS\delta SC$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_vNS\delta SCS$ in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta\beta C$ mapping but not $I_vNS\delta PC$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_vNS\delta\beta CS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_vNS\delta PCS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Example 4.4. In Example 3.4,

- (i) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta C$ mapping but not I_vNSC mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_vNS\delta SCS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not I_vNSCS in \mathbb{T} .
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is $I_vNS\delta SC$ mapping but not $I_vNS\delta\alpha C$ mapping because $(V_1, \varrho)^c$ is $I_vNS\delta SCS$ in \mathbb{T} but $\mathcal{G}(V_1, \varrho)^c = (S_4, \varrho)^c$ is not $I_vNS\delta\alpha CS$ in \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 4.2. A map $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C iff for each $I_vNSS(S, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and for each $I_vNSOS(P, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ containing $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho)$ there is an $I_vNSe^*OS(B, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $(S, \varrho) \subseteq (B, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*C map. Let (S, ϱ) be the I_vNSCS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and (P, ϱ) is a I_vNSOS of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(S, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$. Then $(B, \varrho) = \mathbb{T} - \mathcal{G}^{-1}(P, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSe^*OS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (P, \varrho)$.

Sufficiency: Assume (B, ϱ) is a I_vNSCS of $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))^c$ is a I_vNSS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $(B, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ such that $\mathcal{G}^{-1}((\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))^c) \subseteq (B, \varrho)^c$. By hypothesis there is a $I_vNSe^*O(B, \varrho)$ of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ such that $(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))^c \subseteq (B, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho) \subseteq (B, \varrho)^c$. Therefore $(B, \varrho) \subseteq (\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho))^c$. Hence $(B, \varrho)^c \subseteq \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho) \subseteq \mathcal{G}((\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho))^c) \subseteq (B, \varrho)^c$ which implies $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho) = (B, \varrho)^c$. Since $(B, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSe^*OS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and thus \mathcal{G} is I_vNSe^*C map. ■

Theorem 4.3. If $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSC and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C , then $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C .

Proof. Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSCS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ because \mathcal{G} is I_vNSC map. Now $(\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G})(B, \varrho) = \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))$ is I_vNSe^*C in $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ because \mathcal{H} is I_vNSe^*C map. Thus $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSe^*C map. ■

Theorem 4.4. If $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C map, then $I_vNSe^*cl(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)) \subseteq \mathcal{G}(I_vNScl(B, \varrho))$.

Proof. Obvious. ■

Theorem 4.5. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ be I_vNSe^*C maps. If every I_vNSe^*CS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is I_vNSC then, $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*C .

Proof. Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*CS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ because \mathcal{G} is I_vNSe^*C map. By hypothesis $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSCS of $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Now $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)) =$

$(\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G})(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSe^*CS in $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ because \mathcal{H} is I_vNSe^*C map. Thus $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSe^*C map. ■

Theorem 4.6. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an objective map, then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*O map.
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*C map.
- (iii) \mathcal{G}^{-1} is a I_vNSe^*Cts map.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Let us assume that \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*O map. By definition, (B, ϱ) is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$, then $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSe^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Here, (B, ϱ) is I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$, then $\mathbb{W} - (B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. By assumption, $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{W} - (B, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSe^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence, $\mathbb{T} - \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{W} - (B, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSe^*CS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Therefore, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^*C map.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ By(ii), $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSe^*CS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence, $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho) = (\mathcal{G}^{-1})^{-1}(B, \varrho)$, so \mathcal{G}^{-1} is a I_vNSe^*CS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence, \mathcal{G}^{-1} is I_vNSe^*Cts .

(iii) \Rightarrow (i): Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ By(iii), $(\mathcal{G}^{-1})^{-1}(B, \varrho) = \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSe^*O map. ■

5. Interval - valued neutrosophic soft e^* - homeomorphism

Definition 5.1. A bijection $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is called a I_vNSe^* -homeomorphism (briefly I_vNSe^* Hom) if \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}^{-1} are I_vNSe^*Cts .

Theorem 5.1. Each I_vNSHom is a I_vNSe^* Hom.

Proof. Let \mathcal{G} be I_vNSHom , then \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}^{-1} are I_vNSCts . But every I_vNSCts function is I_vNSe^*Cts . Hence, \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}^{-1} are I_vNSe^*Cts . Therefore, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSe^* Hom. ■

Example 5.1. Let $\mathbb{W} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\} = \mathbb{T}, \varrho = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $I_vNSS (V_1, \varrho)$ and (V_2, ϱ) in \mathbb{W} and (S_1, ϱ) in \mathbb{T} are defined as

$$(V_1, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.6,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(V_1, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.6,0.8]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.5,0.9]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.1,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.7,0.9]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(V_2, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.5,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.2,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.4,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.2,0.3]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(V_2, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_1}}{[0.4,0.7]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_2}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{w_3}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{w_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_1) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.6]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.3,0.4]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle \rangle$$

$$(S_1, e_2) = \langle \langle (\frac{\mu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_1}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_1}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_2}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}, \frac{\nu_{t_2}}{[0.3,0.5]}), (\frac{\mu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.5]}, \frac{\sigma_{t_3}}{[0.5,0.7]}, \frac{\nu_{t_3}}{[0.4,0.6]}) \rangle \rangle$$

Then, we have $\tau = \{0_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{W}, \varrho)}, (V_1, \varrho), (V_2, \varrho)\}$ and $\sigma = \{0_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, 1_{(\mathbb{T}, \varrho)}, (S_1, \varrho)\}$. Let $\mathcal{G}: (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be an identity mapping, then \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*Hom but not I_vNSHom .

Theorem 5.2. $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be a bijective map. If \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*Cts , then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*C map.
- (ii) \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*O map.
- (iii) \mathcal{G}^{-1} is a I_vNSE^*Hom map.

Proof. (i) \rightarrow (ii): Assume that \mathcal{G} is a bijective map and a I_vNSE^*C map. Hence, \mathcal{G}^{-1} is a I_vNSE^*Cts map. We know that each I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*OS map.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) : Let \mathcal{G} be a bijective and I_vNSO map. Further, \mathcal{G}^{-1} is a I_vNSE^*Cts map. Hence, \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}^{-1} are I_vNSE^*Cts . Therefore, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*Hom .

(iii) \Rightarrow (i): Let \mathcal{G} be a I_vNSE^*Hom , then \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}^{-1} are I_vNSE^*Cts . Since each I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*CS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*C map. ■

Definition 5.2. A I_vNSts $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is said to be an interval valued neutrosophic soft $e^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (briefly, $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$)- space if every I_vNSE^*CS is I_vNSC in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$.

Theorem 5.3. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be a I_vNSE^*Hom , then \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSHom if $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ and $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ are $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space.

Proof. Assume that (B, ϱ) is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$, then $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*CS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Since $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$ is an $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ space, $\mathcal{G}^{-1}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Therefore, \mathcal{G} is I_vNSCts . By hypothesis, \mathcal{G}^{-1} is I_vNSE^*Cts . Let (A, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then, $(\mathcal{G}^{-1})^{-1}(A, \varrho) = \mathcal{G}(A, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$, by presumption. Since $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is a $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space, $\mathcal{G}(A, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Hence, \mathcal{G}^{-1} is I_vNSCts . Hence, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSHom . ■

Theorem 5.4. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ be a I_vNSts then the following are equivalent if $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is a $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space.

- (i) \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSE^*C map.
- (ii) If (B, ϱ) is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$, then $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(B, \varrho)) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)))$ for every I_vNSS (B, ϱ) in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Obvious.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then, $I_vNSint(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(B, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Since $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ is a $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(B, \varrho))$ is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$.

Therefore, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(B, \varrho)) = I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint(B, \varrho))) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)))$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i): Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Then, $(B, \varrho)^c$ is a I_vNSOS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. From, $\mathcal{G}(I_vNSint((B, \varrho)^c)) \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)^c))$. Hence, $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)^c \subseteq I_vNScl(I_vNSint(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)^c))$. Therefore, $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)^c$ is I_vNSE^*OS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Therefore, $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*CS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Hence, \mathcal{G} is a I_vNSC map. ■

Theorem 5.5. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ be I_vNSE^*C , where $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ are two $I_vNSTs's$ and $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ a $I_vNSE^*T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space, then the composition $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSE^*C map.

Proof. Let (B, ϱ) be a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho)$. Since \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*C and $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSE^*CS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$, by assumption, $\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$ is a I_vNSCS in $(\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$. Since \mathcal{H} is I_vNSE^*C , $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho))$, is I_vNSE^*C in $(\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)) = \mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}(B, \varrho)$. Therefore, $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSE^*C map. ■

Theorem 5.6. Let $\mathcal{G} : (\mathbb{W}, \tau, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho)$ and $\mathcal{H} : (\mathbb{T}, \sigma, \varrho) \rightarrow (\mathbb{U}, \rho, \varrho)$ be two $I_vNSTs's$ then the following hold:

- (i) if $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSE^*O and \mathcal{G} is I_vNSCts , then \mathcal{H} is I_vNSE^*O map.
- (ii) if $\mathcal{H} \circ \mathcal{G}$ is I_vNSO and \mathcal{H} is I_vNSE^*Cts , then \mathcal{G} is I_vNSE^*O map.

Proof. Obvious. ■

6. Conclusions

The study presented a detailed analysis of interval-valued neutrosophic soft δ -open and δ -closed maps, along with the formulation of the $\delta\beta$ -homeomorphism. The theoretical findings, supported by illustrative examples, enrich the structural understanding of mappings in interval-valued neutrosophic soft topological spaces. These contributions serve as a stepping stone for further mathematical investigation and practical advancements in the study of generalized topological structures under uncertainty.

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